

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS THAT AFFECT PEOPLE TO SHOP IN TRADITIONAL MARKETS AMID COMPETITION WITH MODERN MARKETS STUDY IN 3 CITIES IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

Indonesia is a country that has entered an era of global competition, where there are no limits for individuals or companies to develop businesses, whether small, medium or large. The market is a forum for community activities in buying and selling as the basis of a region's economy. Traditional markets are a forum for farmers/fishermen to sell agricultural products directly and are usually managed by the Government, Regional Government, Private Sector, BUMN and BUMD. Apart from that, there are modern markets. The role of modern markets, especially mini markets in Indonesia, is getting bigger daily, and it is estimated that they will eventually replace traditional markets. Self-service shops or services are carried out by consumers themselves because the shop does not provide sales assistants who specifically serve consumers. This happens because of the shift in consumer preferences, in this case, preferences in shopping. The scope of this research is in the cities of Kupang, Malang, and Yogyakarta, where the researcher limits the scope to traditional markets in the city area and includes market traders and consumers, traditional markets, and modern retailers. This research used a qualitative approach. This was done so that researchers could describe the occurrence of social phenomena in the traditional markets of Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta with the existence of modern retailers. Several factors are identified in this research, and several factors are the most dominant. These factors include the bargaining process, prices for goods are lower, earlier opening hours, completeness and a variety of choices, no need to dress up or wear nice clothes, and the products being fresher.

Keywords: Shopping, Traditional Markets, Modern Markets

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country that has entered an era of global competition, where there are no limits for individuals or companies to develop businesses, whether small, medium or large. With the development of global competition which cannot be stopped, it has resulted in small businesses being unable to compete with medium and large businesses in the business world. The trade sector has made a large contribution to Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The market is a place where economic activities occur. The market is where transactions take place where sellers meet to market their wares and buyers who want to fulfill their daily needs. In the interaction market, there is often a bargaining system between sellers and buyers, this has become part of the social culture of Indonesian society to this day that is still being done. Markets like this are called traditional markets. But in general, the market Traditionally throughout Indonesia, comfort facilities are the main problem. Traditional markets seem dirty, shabby, smelly, and so on, making buyers uncomfortable.

The market is a forum for community activities in buying and selling as the basis of the economy of a region. Traditional markets are a forum for farmers/fishermen to sell agricultural products directly and are usually managed by the Government, Regional Government, Private Sector, BUMN and BUMD. The Advanced Indonesia Cabinet's target to increase the role of traditional markets is to revitalize 5,000 traditional markets that are more than 25 years old. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency, traditional markets in Indonesia are numbered in 14,182 units. In 2019, the eight provinces with the largest distribution of traditional markets were East Java (2,249 units), Central Java (1,910 units) and North Sumatra (858 units). Then followed by West Java (817 markets), South Sulawesi (768 units), Riau (690 units) and Lampung (639 units). Meanwhile traditional markets still dominate public trade centers, reaching 14,182 units (88.52%) while modern shops account for 1,131 units (7.06%). Colliers International data shows that there will be the addition of three shopping centers in Jakarta and three in Bodetabek. Overall, additional supply is predicted to reach 600,000 square meters in the 2019-2021 period, 70% of which will be in the capital. Currently, the largest shopping centers are in West Java (121 units), DKI Jakarta (88 units), East Java (79 units) and Banten (37 units). Apart from shopping centers, the role of modern markets, especially mini markets, in Indonesia is increasing day by day and is predicted to eventually replace traditional markets. Self-service shops or services are carried out by consumers themselves because the shop does not provide sales assistants who specifically serve consumers. This happens because of a shift in consumer preferences, in this case preferences in shopping. Easy to reach location, comfortable and safe atmosphere in shopping; It's easy to choose the items you need, which is an attraction for shopping in supermarkets. With the development of the times to meet people's expectations, modern retail has been formed which prioritizes the convenience of buyers by implementing a strategy of prioritizing cleanliness, good service, and including price tags on each product, so that people can find out the price of these goods without haggling with the seller. This is a very prominent difference from traditional markets. Currently there are several modern retailers that also compete with other modern retailers.

Judging from the place of purchase, people are more likely to buy fresh food at greengrocers and traditional markets. This is shown by 70% of respondents buying fresh food ingredients at food stalls or greengrocers, followed by 58% of respondents buying directly at the market. Only 9% choose to buy at supermarkets or hypermarkets. Meanwhile, when it comes to purchasing household necessities, not fresh food, people prefer to shop at modern retailers. As many as 67% of respondents chose to shop at supermarkets, 40% at stalls or greengrocers and 16% bought directly at the market.

The Ministry of Trade (Kemendag) revealed that currently the number of modern markets throughout Indonesia in 2022 will reach 23,000 units. This number has increased by 14 % in the last three years. There are 23,000 modern markets and of that number, more than 14,000 of them are minimarket business groups, while the rest are supermarkets. According to a Jakpat survey of 2,000 respondents, the majority or 34.3% routinely buy monthly household necessities at supermarkets. Then as many as 20.05% of respondents routinely shop monthly at traditional markets, 16.35% at grocery stalls, and 15.20% at supermarkets. From this survey it can be concluded that although the number of traditional markets is greater than modern markets such as supermarkets, most people prefer to shop at supermarkets rather than traditional

markets. This is a threat for traders in traditional markets if they do not want to be unable to compete with modern markets which are growing very quickly. Several tips from the government to maintain the existence of traditional markets by revitalizing traditional markets in Indonesia to be able to remain competitive with modern retail.

Figure 1

Traditional markets have many roles for both society and the government. Traditional markets are used as a place to market various kinds of products ranging from food, drinks, clothing, souvenir products, crafts, stationery and others. Another role of traditional markets is as a forum for increasing employment opportunities, increasing people's income and reducing poverty rates. The existence of traditional markets plays an important role as the foundation of the economy in a region. In this research, the objects are traditional markets in the cities of Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta. The unfavorable image of traditional markets must receive serious treatment from the government because it concerns the lives of many people. Improving traditional markets to become shopping places that are comfortable, attractive and have a positive image is quite a tough challenge that the government must undertake as a sense of responsibility to the public. The existence of traditional markets must also receive more serious attention from the government. The government must also encourage traditional markets to make changes to services like modern retail which must be developed by traditional markets so that they are not left out in the competition for consumers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Marketing Strategy

Kotler and Armstrong (2013) marketing strategy is the marketing logic in which a business unit hopes to achieve its marketing goals. Boone and Kurtz (2008) marketing strategy is a company's overall program in determining market targets and satisfying consumers by building a combination of elements from the marketing mix, product, distribution, promotion and price. Kotler (2000) marketing strategy is a marketing mindset that will be used to achieve marketing goals, where there is a detailed strategy regarding the target market, positioning, marketing mix, and budget for marketing.

Marketing strategy is a plan that allows a company to optimize the use of its resources to achieve marketing and corporate goals. Marketing strategy can also be interpreted as an effort to market a product, be it goods or services, using certain plans and tactics so that the number of sales is higher. Marketing strategy consists of the basic principles that underlie management to achieve business and marketing goals in a target market, marketing strategy contains basic decisions about marketing, and the marketing mix.

2.2 Consumer behavior

Consumer Behavior Griffin and Ebbert (2006) say that to understand consumer preferences in purchasing a product, you must first know consumer behavior. Consumer behavior is the study of consumer decision processes that encourage them to buy and consume goods or services. Various definitions have been put forward by several economists regarding consumer behavior. There are several definitions regarding consumer behavior along with the opinions of several experts regarding consumer behavior. According to Engel, et al. (2006) consumer behavior is the actions carried out by a consumer in obtaining, consuming and disposing of products and services, these actions include the decision processes that precede and follow these actions. While Hawkins, et al. (2007) describes consumer behavior as an individual, group or organization and the processes used to select, convince, use and place products, services and experiences, or ideas to satisfy needs and the impact of this process on consumers. From this definition it can be concluded that consumer behavior is a series of actions carried out related to the decision-making process in obtaining goods and services by both individual and household consumers. Marketing must be able to understand diverse consumer behavior. Marketers who understand consumer behavior will be able to predict how consumers will act on the information they receive so that the products and services marketed by marketers can be more competitive with other similar products.

2.3 Traditional market

According to Presidential Regulation no. 112 of 2007, traditional markets are markets built and managed by the central government, regional governments, state-owned companies, and private parties whose business premises are kiosks, shops, tents, and stalls owned or managed by small, medium-sized traders, cooperatives, non-governmental organizations. where the buying and selling process is carried out through a bargaining process. According to Sadilah, et al (2011), a traditional market is an open place where the bargaining process takes place. In this traditional market, visitors are not always buyers because they can also be sellers. Traditional markets can be classified into 3 forms, namely special markets, periodic markets, and daily markets. According to Gallion (1986), traditional markets are the earliest form of markets which consist of rows of stands or kiosks in open spaces and are generally located along main roads near residential areas. Since ancient times, traders and farmers have exchanged their agricultural products in places like this.

Generally, traditional markets are found on urban outskirts/roads or residential areas. Traditional markets include household shops/stalls, kiosks, street vendors and so on. The goods sold here are almost the same as the goods sold in modern markets with various types. However, traditional markets tend to sell only local goods and rarely find imported goods. Because the goods sold in traditional markets tend to be the same as modern markets, the goods sold have relatively the same guaranteed quality

as goods in modern markets. In terms of quantity, traditional markets generally have a small supply of goods according to the capital owned by the owner or demand from consumers. In terms of price, traditional markets do not have a definite price tag because the price is adjusted to the amount of profit desired by each individual business owner.

2.4 Modern market

Modern Market, created market and managed very well using modern management, in the opinion of Sinaga (2006). A modern market is a market that does not involve direct seller and buyer transactions, because the price of the product is clearly listed (Kotler; 2001). Sinaga (2006) said that modern markets are markets managed with modern management, generally found in urban areas, as providers of goods and services with good quality and service to consumers (generally members of the upper middle class). Modern markets include malls, supermarkets, department stores, shopping centers, franchises, mini supermarkets, convenience markets, and convenience stores and so on. The presence of the modern market is a consequence of society's increasingly developing lifestyle. Previously, this market was mostly found in big cities, but now its existence has reached small areas. The various comfortable facilities and affordable prices offered in modern markets are one of the attractions for the community.

2.5 Reasons why people shop at traditional markets

In general, the definition of a traditional market is a place where local sellers meet with buyers to carry out a transaction accompanied by bargaining so that a price agreement is reached. Recently, traditional markets have begun to be pushed aside due to the increasing number of minimarkets and supermarkets, even in remote places, it is not surprising that the existence of traditional markets has begun to be underestimated by the public. Even though shopping at traditional markets has many benefits, Mahany (2015) said there are 10 reasons why you should shop at traditional markets rather than supermarkets.

1. You can bargain, unlike in supermarkets where prices cannot be negotiated
2. More complete and with lots of choices, the goods in traditional markets are also much more complete than in supermarkets, let alone minimarkets.
3. Buying domestic products means you love Indonesian products. If you love Indonesia, it means it's time for you to start shopping for your needs in traditional markets.
4. Fresher products, apart from being more complete, products in traditional markets are usually fresher.
5. There is no need to dress up or wear nice clothes, this reason is specifically for those who are usually lazy about dressing up or lazy about changing clothes.
6. Opening hours are earlier, unlike supermarkets, traditional markets usually open much earlier.
7. Traditional markets are no less comfortable, people's view when they hear about traditional markets is that the place is messy, rubbish is strewn about, it's muddy when it rains.

8. Prices of goods are cheaper, unlike supermarkets, traditional markets have much cheaper prices because visitors can bargain at the traditional market.
9. You can become more familiar with traders, if we often shop at traditional markets, usually the traders will remember that we are regular customers.
10. Buying at a traditional market means you are supporting small businesses. The increasing number of minimarkets and supermarkets has caused the income of traders in traditional markets to decrease slightly.

Meanwhile, according to Hapsari (2022), there are several reasons why people should try to shop at traditional markets because there are several advantages that cannot be found in modern markets. Even though the place is not as clean as a supermarket, it turns out there are many benefits to going there.

1. The affordable prices mean you can save money, it's natural that the prices of goods sold in traditional markets are cheaper than modern markets where the location is good. By shopping at traditional markets you can save money and put aside a lot of money for savings
2. The price is often still negotiable, it is cheap and still negotiable. This is very profitable for society and cannot be obtained from the modern market.
3. The goods sold are usually fruits, vegetables, fish, and meat sold in traditional markets are usually fresh.
4. Can support local farmers' economy, agricultural products sold in traditional markets usually come from local farmers. If their agricultural products sell well, then their economy will improve.
5. There is good communication between sellers and buyers. In traditional markets, when making a purchase there must be a conversation between the seller and the buyer. Not just for bargaining, but also for exchanging information. For example, regarding issues surrounding the price and availability of goods, from there buyers get information about agricultural products.
6. While shopping, you can also buy market snacks, there are many unique things in traditional markets such as other market snacks which are usually sold in traditional markets. If you go to a traditional market, it feels like something is missing if you don't buy the snacks at the same time. Apart from its delicious taste, this traditional cake is also not sold in many other places.

3. METHODS

3.1 The scope of research

The scope of this research is the Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta City areas, where the researcher limits the scope to Traditional Markets in the city area and includes market traders and market consumers, traditional markets, and modern retailers.

3.2 Types of research

The research used is research with a qualitative approach. This was done so that researchers could describe the occurrence of social phenomena in the traditional markets of Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta with the existence of modern retailers. By using in-depth interviews, researchers can explore objects, namely traditional market

traders as well as market consumers and modern retail consumers. A qualitative approach is used to obtain in-depth data, data that contains meaning. So later we will explain and deepen the Strategy of Traditional Market Traders in Facing Modern Retail Competition.

3.3 Sampling technique

The sampling method in this research is Non-probability sampling, which is "a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample" (Sugiyono, 2018). The sampling technique in this research uses a non-probability sampling method through judgmental sampling techniques. Researchers choose judgmental sampling based on which population is considered most appropriate to the researcher's aims and objectives (Malhotra, 2010). Researchers use this research technique because it does not take much time and is more efficient. In this research, the sample used was calculated using the Lemeshow formula. The Lemeshow formula is used to calculate samples in unknown population conditions. The calculations used are as follows:

$$N = \frac{Z.P.(1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where:

N = Number of Samples

Z = z distribution value at 5% CI

P = maximum probability estimate

d = alpha

$$N = 96 \frac{1,64.0,5.(1-0,5)}{0,05^2}$$

The results of the calculation formula above are 96 people who will be used as samples/informants in this research.

3.4 Data collection technique

Data collection activities are efforts carried out by researchers to obtain related data or information for fulfillment in compiling research results. The techniques used to obtain these data are observation, interviews, questionnaires, and data documentation.

3.5 Analysis Method

In this research, the method used is descriptive analysis using a non-statistical approach which accurately describes a situation and phenomenon. What is meant by a descriptive model is a research method that attempts to describe and interpret objects according to what they are. The number of informants in this research was 90 visitors and sellers in the traditional markets of Kupang City, Malang and Yogyakarta. Data collection techniques use interviews, documentation and observation. Data analysis techniques according to Miles & Huberman (1992), analysis consists of three streams of activities that occur simultaneously, namely: data reduction, data presentation, drawing conclusions/verification.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research the author identified at least 12 factors that make people continue to shop at traditional markets compared to modern market supermarkets.

Table 1: Reasons for Shopping at Traditional Markets

NO	Reasons to Shop	Score			Total
		Kupang	Poor	Yogyakarta	
1	Can bargain	126	119	136	381
2	more complete and lots of choices	35	60	52	147
3	Buying domestic products means loving Indonesian products	6	11	9	26
4	fresher product	40	38	54	132
5	no need to dress up or wear nice clothes	75	46	16	137
6	earlier opening hours	35	68	77	180
7	Traditional markets are no less comfortable	15	10	10	35
8	cheaper goods prices	58	87	81	226
9	can become more familiar with traders	23	3	17	43
10	Buying at a traditional market means you are supporting small businesses	7	23	15	45
11	social interaction	41	12	26	79
12	lots of unique things	2	3	0	5

From the table above, it can be seen that there are several dominant reasons why people choose to shop at traditional markets rather than modern markets/supermarkets;

1. You can bargain, unlike in supermarkets where prices cannot be negotiated. If you shop at traditional markets, you can freely bargain the price as you like. The better you are at bargaining, the cheaper the price of the goods you will get. Even though it sounds easy, bargaining is not easy, sometimes the price may or may not go down.
2. Prices of goods are cheaper, unlike supermarkets, traditional markets have much cheaper prices because visitors can bargain. This is one of the attractions because sellers usually get goods directly from farmers or directly from small businesses who are their suppliers, and are not subject to large taxes.
3. Opening hours are earlier, unlike supermarkets, traditional markets usually open much earlier. This makes it easier for those who have culinary businesses to buy the goods they need, and this can only be done if we shop at traditional markets.
4. More complete and with lots of choices, the goods in traditional markets are also much more complete than in supermarkets, let alone minimarkets. Almost all your needs are available in traditional markets, from raw materials, vegetables, fruit, household items, to even underwear. Apart from being able to bargain and being cheaper, if you buy at traditional markets the goods are much more complete, goods that are not available in supermarkets are usually available at traditional markets.
5. There is no need to dress up or wear nice clothes, this reason is specifically for those who are usually lazy about dressing up or lazy about changing clothes. If you shop at traditional markets, you can just use normal ones, it won't be a problem.

6. Fresher products, apart from being more complete, products in traditional markets are usually fresher. The goods sold are usually fresh, all fruit, vegetables, fish and meat sold in traditional markets are usually fresh. This happens because collectors always stock goods early in the morning to sell that day, so the goods are fresher and the process takes place every day.

Apart from the factors mentioned above, there are several factors that make people continue to shop at traditional markets, including; social interaction, traditional markets are a place of social interaction for the community.

The interactions that took place were quite interesting, such as bargaining with each other, which led to more intense conversations among fellow buyers; Buying at a traditional market means you are supporting small businesses, traditional markets sell more of their own country's produce. If we shop at traditional markets, we are helping to promote domestic products. Shopping at traditional markets is the same as helping to develop domestic small businesses; You can become more familiar with traders. Not only fellow buyers, interesting interactions also occur with fellow sellers using their respective regional languages.

That's what gives a special warmth when shopping at traditional markets; Traditional markets are no less comfortable, many traditional markets have now been revitalized so they are no less comfortable. In traditional markets we also don't have to queue to pay at the cashier like what happens in supermarkets. Especially if on weekends the payment queue can be busier; Buying domestic products means loving Indonesian products. Most of the products sold in traditional markets are the result of small businesses from the local community.

Therefore, if we shop at traditional markets, it will indirectly help the small business economy grow. ; there are many unique things, for example in traditional markets we can find sellers of complete cooking spices that are ready to be mixed, the prices are not too expensive. All you must do is say what you are going to cook, and the seasoning seller will quickly mix it, something you do not find anywhere else.

5. CONCLUSION

Of the several factors identified in this research, in terms of marketing strategies of traditional market traders regarding people's decisions to shop at traditional markets, there are several factors that are the most dominant. These factors include; You can bargain, shopping at traditional markets is actually much cheaper. Because the traders there are not too dependent on production costs and other things that burden the price of the goods they sell; Cheaper price of goods; Shopping at traditional markets is actually much cheaper. Because the traders there do not really focus on production costs and other things that burden the price of the goods they sell. From several chats with regular traders, they said that a small profit is not the important thing, the important thing is that the sales run out, and there is no loss. Opening hours are earlier, different from the opening hours of modern markets, traditional markets usually start operating in the early hours of the morning and some are even open 24 hours.

This certainly makes it easier for people who have culinary businesses to buy raw materials for their production; More complete and with lots of choices, many traders offer their merchandise at various prices and types of goods, so that buyers can freely choose which ones they are interested in; There is no need to dress up or wear nice clothes, the healthiest social interactions are only in traditional markets. Sellers will not

differentiate in their attitudes as long as we transact fairly and end up buying their merchandise. Whether dressed in parlente or negligee, traditional markets make no distinction; Fresher products. Products sold in traditional markets are usually fresher. Various fresh fish, vegetables, various traditional foods/cakes. Because collectors usually work early in the morning so that the goods, they stock can be sold that day.

6. SUGGESTION

Based on the research that has been carried out regarding the marketing strategies of traditional market traders in facing competition with modern markets/supermarkets, suggestions can be made for several parties which will hopefully be considered for the good of each party. The following are some of the suggestions made:

1. Traditional market traders must be better prepared to compete with modern retail. Even though research states that there is no influence on traditional market traders, this must be watched out for from now on. A special strategy is needed to overcome the possibility that the existence of modern markets/supermarkets could displace the existence of traditional markets in the cities of Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta. The strategy that traditional market traders must improve is to care about their stalls by always paying attention to their merchandise being neatly arranged and maintaining cleanliness so that it attracts consumers to shop. Being neatly arranged makes sales transactions easier because it is easy to find the goods that people want. Consumers will be happy if the service is provided quickly. As well as complementing the supply of merchandise needed by the public, this creates a sense of consumer satisfaction. Sometimes consumers buy goods at kiosks that are incomplete and the next day they don't want to come back because they feel dissatisfied. As well as maintaining price stability to be able to compete with existing modern retailers.
2. The Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta City Governments must be more concerned with the existence of traditional markets which they feel will be threatened by modern markets/supermarkets which are developing rapidly. The role of the government here is really needed to regulate and maintain the balance of business competition in the cities of Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta, especially between traditional markets and modern markets. The Kupang, Malang and Yogyakarta City Governments must also improve services to the community, especially traditional market traders whose existence is felt to be threatened by the existence of modern retail. Things that must be done by the government are: a) facilitating access to capital loan assistance for traditional markets so that they can expand their business; b) the government should pay more attention to traditional markets, namely in terms of places where traditional market traders sell and in terms of permits for the increasing number of Modern Markets/Supermarkets to enter; c) infrastructure improvements that include ensuring proper health, adequate cleanliness, sufficient light, and overall comfort of the market environment; d) joint ventures (in the form of work agreements) between regional governments and the private sector can also be the best solution to increase the competitiveness of traditional markets; e) the government must curb thugs and extortion or collecting illegal fees in traditional markets; f) the government must determine the distance between traditional markets and modern markets/supermarkets which are far apart, as well as the size of Modern Retail businesses; g) Zoning, namely the division of zones/areas for certain types of retail so as to prevent unbalanced

competition; h) The need for a Retail Law as a framework and foundation for the government in managing the modern retail sector so as not to kill traditional markets and maximizing the contribution of modern retail to the local economy is urgently needed.

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